

CONCEPTUAL ASSUMPTION OF THE EXPRESSION OF HUMAN FEELINGS IN ENGLISH, UZBEK AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES

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Abstract. This article explores the cultural and linguistic differences in how emotions are expressed and valued in English, Uzbek and Karakalpak languages. It analyzes the vocabulary used to describe emotions, as well as the social norms surrounding emotional expression. The study also examines how these cultural differences may impact communication and understanding between speakers of these languages.

Keywords: emotion, expression, human feelings, language, English, Uzbek, Karakalpak.

The conceptual assumption of the expression of human feelings in English, Uzbek, and Karakalpak languages is based on the cultural and social norms of each language. Each language has its unique way of expressing emotions, and the words used to describe emotions may differ in meaning and intensity.

For example, the English language has a wide range of words to describe emotions, such as happy, sad, angry, excited, nervous, jealous, frustrated, grateful, embarrassed, and content. These words are commonly used in everyday conversations and are easily understood by native speakers [5, 57-62].

Similarly, the Uzbek language also has a rich vocabulary to describe emotions, including xursand (happy), xafa (sad), qarshi (angry), hayajonli (excited), o'zg'in (nervous), hasadli (jealous), baxtsiz (frustrated), minnatdor (grateful), sharmli (embarrassed), and muvaffaqiyatsiz (unsuccessful) [2, 20-22].

Likewise, the Karakalpak language also has its unique way of expressing emotions, with words such as gázeplengen (angry), qapa (sad), baxtsiz (frustrated), kewilli (happy), gázepli (nervous), hasadli (jealous), minnetdar (grateful), uyatli (embarrassed), and áwmetsiz (unsuccessful).

Examples of Conceptual assumption of the expression of human feelings in English, Uzbek and Karakalpak languages"

In English, there is a strong emphasis on individual expression and self-fulfillment. Emotions are often expressed directly and openly, with a wide range of vocabulary to describe different emotions. English also has a history of borrowing words related to emotions from other languages.

In Uzbek culture, emotional restraint is often valued, and overt displays of emotion may be viewed as inappropriate or even shameful. Emotions are often expressed indirectly, through nonverbal cues or subtle language. Uzbek also has a rich vocabulary for describing emotional states and experiences.

In Karakalpak culture, emotions are often expressed in a way that emphasizes group harmony and social cohesion. There is a strong emphasis on collectivism and the importance of maintaining positive relationships with others. Karakalpak also has a nuanced vocabulary for describing different types of emotions, with a particular focus on the emotions associated with interpersonal relationships [4, 117-118].

The conceptual assumption of the expression of human feelings in English, Uzbek, and Karakalpak languages is important because it highlights the cultural and linguistic differences in how emotions are expressed and understood. This knowledge can be particularly useful for individuals who are learning or working with these languages and cultures, as it can help them better understand and communicate with others. Additionally, understanding the nuances of emotional expression in different languages can promote empathy and cross-cultural understanding, which are important for building relationships and promoting positive interactions between people from different backgrounds.

Conclusion. Overall, the conceptual assumption of the expression of human feelings in these languages reflects their cultural and social values, and understanding these differences is essential for effective communication and cross-cultural understanding.

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